

IMPROVING THE MODERN STYLE OF DESIGNING AND STRUCTURING AGRICULTURAL CARDS

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Annotation: *This article provides information on improving the modern method of designing and compiling agricultural cards, designing and compiling cards, editing cards and the tasks of card design.*

Keywords: *map, design, compilation, editing, photography, astronomical, topographic, photography sources, cartographic, geographic, economic-statistical, aerospace photos.*

Introduction.

In the conditions of water shortage in the world, the rational use of water for irrigation of agricultural crops is of particular importance. In this regard, secondary salinization of the soil, salinization, rise of flood waters, swamping of lands and the formation of collector-drainage-discharge saline waters, occurrence of dehumification processes, proper organization of direct irrigation. One of the important issues is the improvement of the method of calculating the rate of irrigation of agricultural crops. In this regard, in the leading countries, the USA, China, India and other countries, it is necessary to evaluate the efficiency of water use in irrigation networks, determine the criteria for water use when water supply decreases, determine the impact on crops, and take into account the demand for water once and seasonally. Special attention is paid to the calculation of irrigation standards according to the FAO (guideline for determining plant water requirements) methodology and the SROPWAT program.[1-5]

In the action strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, an important task is to pay special attention to, among other things, "...the application of intensive methods to the field of agricultural production, first of all, modern agro-technologies that save water and resources." Scientific research on saving irrigation water and improving land reclamation through the most convenient and effective improvement of the method of

calculating irrigation regimes and rates of agricultural crops is of great importance for the implementation of this task.

To implement the tasks specified in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4947 of February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and other regulatory and legal documents related to this activity this dissertation research serves to a certain extent [1-10].

Methods.

Many scientists have conducted scientific research on the scientific basis and problems of developing the basis of a modern system of methods for creating an agricultural map and its effective and rational use. Deepening of economic reforms and liberalization of the economy, as well as the full use of remote sensing systems in the conditions of increasing demand for land resources in all areas of our republic, were not sufficiently expressed in their scientific work.

Results and Discussion.

Creating cards involves many technological processes.

Cards are basically 2 ways:

1. By direct field surveying (phototopographical method) and special surveying, such as geological surveying, soil surveying (cadastral surveying), geobotanical, geophysical surveying, etc. works with .

2. It is compiled by special expert cartographers on the basis of various sources and data (astronomical, topographical, survey sources, cartographic, geographical, economic-statistical, aerospace pictures and other sources) collected in camera conditions, i.e. in the office. . Current cartography textbooks and manuals provide information on creating topographic and geographical maps in field and camera conditions.

But even in field conditions, there are also large and medium-scale thematic maps based on topographical maps. Special sciences such as soil science cartography, geobotanical cartography and other sciences teach ways of creating maps.

There are 3 cartographic terms in cartography. They are: designing, editing and creating cards.

Designing cards means creating a new card and modernizing existing cards.

Editing of cards refers to methods of developing editorial documents for card creation and guiding scientific and technical work in the process of card creation[11-15].

Mapping of maps means the method of creating an initial copy of the map, which is a copy that reflects the mathematical basis, the content of the map, and a generalized cartographic description.

The purpose of the design is to organize and evaluate the work carried out in the process of creating or updating the card.

Card design tasks include:

a) development of technical tasks together with the customer, development of its general program in the case of large cartographic works;

b) development of the mathematical basis of the card (scale, projection, format (size), composition, in the case of an atlas, its layout composition);

c) development of the content of the card, preparation of conventional signs, methods of description, experimental copy and author's model (copy);

g) to develop a way to make the card in an easy and cheap way in a high-quality way;

d) planning and implementation of organizational work necessary to create maps and atlases;

j) development of the technical and economic basis of maps and atlases [16-20].

Card software is the basis of design. This process includes the following: the name of the map area, who it is intended for, cartographic type, type, topics of maps and atlases, mathematical basis, content of maps, principles of generalization, methods and forms of representation, statistical and cartographic sources, the order of their use. and card or atlas preparation technology.

In addition to the program, technical-economic calculations, technical-organizational works and the scientific-technical project of the card. The project of the created card and atlas not only provides complete information about the card or atlas being created, but also its full value and cost, certain technological processes of the card and atlas, preparation of the author's model, preparation of a copy for editing and the execution times of the publishing model preparation processes are also shown [21-25].

The above-mentioned works are completed, awarded by experts and customers, and only after they are approved, they are considered the main document and work is started.

The design of maps and atlases is divided into the following stages:

- purpose and topics of maps and atlases;

- determining the list of atlas cards;
- developing a mathematical basis;
- preparation of a layout composition;
- creating a list of cartographic and other sources;
- to develop the content of the card and classify and identify the details and objects, events and phenomena to be depicted;
- development of conventional symbols, development of ways of artistically equipping cards and atlases, decoration of the frame and its outside, cut and additional cards, as well as decorating the upper parts of the atlas, open spaces on the cards with photos and pictures;
- developing a card program;
- development of work process technology;
- development of types of geographical bases for atlases and determination of content of author's layouts;
- calculation of costs for each work process;
- development of a work schedule for processes;

The main document of the scientific and technical project (ITL) is the program of the card. The map and atlas type has the following sections:

- the name of the card, its use and requirements for them;
- the mathematical basis of the card;
- the content of the card, methods of description and principles of generalization;
- showing cartographic resources and ways of using them;
- recommendations for geographic characterization and generalization;
- card creation technology.

The solution to issues related to editing, composition and design should be indicated in the program. For example, writing editing instructions and developing legends for each type of card are shown [26-30].

In the technological part of the program, the new technological methods that can be used in the creation of maps and atlases, that is, the possibilities of using computers, EXMs and other new equipment, were shown.

When creating maps and atlases, it is necessary to be able to choose and use conditional symbols on the spot. Conventional signs should be chosen in a simple form, worthy of the content, and at the same time, it should be compatible with modern technology.

Cartographic enterprises have a photo album of special conventional signs, and use that album.

The legend is very important in creating a card, that's why the legend is also called the key of the card. Because it reveals the contents of the card. Before reading the card, get acquainted with its legend. The legend of the card is developed together with the card program and supplied with a copy of the card design.

When developing a legend, conditional symbols should not only match the content of the card, but should also be logically complete, simple, fluid and short. Authorship layouts (copy) are made by highly qualified specialists in specially specialized organizations, people working in the field of maps and cartographer-editors[30-35].

Card authors can work in the following order:

- after the idea of creating a card appears, its content is clarified;
- card program is created;
- sources are studied;
- the initial legend of the card is developed, indicators are determined and scales are selected;
- a copy of the initial sketch (canvas) of the card is prepared;
- resources are developed, additional cross-section cards, graphs, schemes are prepared;
- the full legend of the card is developed;
- an author's copy of the card is made;
- an explanatory letter is written on the author's copy.

It is beneficial to create a map outline program together with a cartographer-editor.

The copy of the authorship is accepted by the editors. In cartographic enterprises, if the author's copy is made at a high level and fully complies with all laws, it can be directly transferred to the publication process without a copy of its composition. This shortens the workflow and speeds up publishing.

Designing cards is the most difficult and responsible task in the preparation of cards. That is why great attention was paid to this process.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it is necessary to say that in today's age of intensive development, advanced information, new technologies, the use of modern methods in the creation of maps and plans used in the organization of the land cadastre, and high-level performance, will allow the effective use of all resources in the development of the country's economy.

The development of the economy of our republic on the path of radical intensive development, the rapid application of scientific and technical development to all sectors and industries, the operation of the agro-industrial complex as a single economic organism, and the implementation of new and priority directions in land use require. Collection, processing, analysis of the necessary information on the amount, categories, types, quality of land and land users aimed at land accounting, land resource management, rational and effective use of the Republic's land fund and land protection, and is unmatched today. becomes important.

Our most important wealth is the motherland, our living space, the place where all our needs are located, the place where we are fed, clothed, and ultimately old. We must consider every aspect of this sacred wealth and use it wisely and effectively. For the purpose of writing the article, when we studied the level of accounting for the massive land fund, arable land, and the use of modern methods for creating a map, I was convinced that there are still very big and urgent tasks in this field, and it is necessary to further improve it.

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